

Sample ID **3-4 (Combined)**

Operator ID **user**

Notes

Elapsed Time	00:01:00
Median Diam.	173.1 nm
Mean Diam.	204.5 nm
Polydispersity	0.396
GSD	1.782

Lognormal Size Distribution

d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)
66.9	26	5	149.6	97	40	255.5	80	75
82.5	44	10	160.9	99	45	281.5	70	80
95.1	58	15	173.1	100	50	314.9	58	85
106.4	70	20	186.2	99	55	363.0	44	90
117.3	80	25	200.3	97	60	447.7	26	95
127.9	87	30	216.2	93	65			
138.6	93	35	234.3	87	70			